

Loop electrosurgical excision procedure in Greek patients with vulvar intraepithelial neoplasia

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Summary

Objective: The aim of our study was to evaluate the therapeutic effectiveness of loop electrosurgical excision procedure (LEEP) in Greek patients with vulvar intraepithelial neoplasia (VIN). **Materials and Methods:** Between January 2002 and January 2009, 55 women with histologically confirmed VIN usual type were included in our study. For the LEEP procedure we used a high frequency electrosurgical unit with at least 80 W output. The tissue was removed to the second surgical plane. Statistical analyses were performed using the SPSS-13 for Windows. **Results:** Complete response rate at 12-month follow-up was 100%. Complete response rate at 48 months of follow-up was 80%. Recurrence rate at 48 months of follow-up was 20%. **Conclusion:** LEEP may constitute a valuable excisional method for the treatment of VIN. It provides an interpretable specimen of the whole lesion within a few minutes. It needs a short period of training and has low cost.

Key words: Electrosurgery; LEEP; Vulvar intraepithelial neoplasia; VIN.

Introduction

Vulvar intraepithelial neoplasia (VIN) is a premalignant lesion involving mostly the non-hairy skin of the vulva. There are two distinct types, the usual VIN type (warty, basaloid and mixed) and the differentiated VIN type [1]. The two types differ in morphology, biology and clinical features [1, 2].

The usual VIN type is related to human papilloma virus (HPV). It occurs predominantly in younger patients and tends to be a multifocal and multicentric disease [1, 2]. It carries the same demographic risk factors as those observed in women with cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) [3]. VIN is caused by high-risk HPV types (primarily 16, 18 and 31) and coexists with other multicentric intraepithelial lesions in the lower genital tract [4-7]. It is seen adjacent to approximately 30% of squamous cell carcinomas (SCC) of the vulva (basaloid and warty type) [1, 2].

The differentiated VIN type is not related to HPV. It occurs less commonly, mainly in older women, and is often observed in association with keratinizing SCC [1, 2].

VIN 3 has a certain invasive potential both in treated (3.3%) and untreated (9%) patients. The progression to invasion may occur many years after VIN 3 has been diagnosed [8, 9] and spontaneous regression may occur (1.2%) [8].

Treatment protocols use either surgical procedures (partial superficial vulvectomy, loop electrosurgical excision procedure (LEEP) and laser CO₂ surgery) or topical medical therapies (5% 5-fluorouracil, 5% imiquimod) [4].

The aim of our study was to evaluate the therapeutic effectiveness of LEEP in Greek patients with VIN.

Material and Methods

Between January 2002 and January 2007, 55 women with histologically confirmed usual type VIN were referred to the 2nd Department of Gynecology of St. Savvas Anticancer-Oncologic Hospital of Athens. Only patients with lesions ≥ 2 cm² in total extent were included in the study. Women with the differentiated VIN type or with recurrent VIN, and pregnant women were excluded from the study.

The total extent of disease was measured prior to LEEP by recording the length and width of all lesional tissues and calculating the total area involved. Prior biopsy sites were not included in the measurements.

For local anesthesia two hours before the operation we used an eutectic mixture of lidocaine and prilocaine on the vulva and one suppository diclophenac per rectum. A few minutes before the operation 2% lidocaine solution diluted with normal saline (1:10) was used to infiltrate the subepithelial papillary dermis beneath and about 1 cm adjacent to the treatment fields.

In all women the lesional tissue was treated with LEEP-6 mm away from the lesion margins (5 mm for free-lesion margins and 1 mm for thermal effect). The tissue was removed to the second surgical plane (reticular dermis). Depth was controlled by performing procedures at high magnification under colposcopic guidance.

For the LEEP procedure we used a high frequency electrosurgical unit with at least 80 W output. For electroexcision we used a 2.5 cm rectangular loop electrode and we selected the blend cut mode with 30 W power output. We created an 18 mm rectangular loop from a stainless steel wire or transformed the semicircular shape of the common loops into a rectangular form with a width up to 2.5 cm. For electrofulguration we used a 5 mm ball electrode and we selected blend coagulation mode with 50 W power output.

All patients were advised to have only protected intercourse during the first six weeks following the procedure and to return for follow-up at six weeks (or earlier if recurrence was noted). The post-treatment follow-up protocol included physical and colposcopic assessment at three, six, nine and 12 months for the first year and yearly thereafter.

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Complete response was defined as no clinical and colposcopic evidence of any vulvar lesion. Partial response was defined as reduction of total VIN area by more than 50%. Recurrence was defined as development of new lesional epithelium in complete responders.

The study was approved by the Ethical Committee of the Hospital. Written informed consent was obtained from each woman.

Statistical analyses were performed using the SPSS-13 for Windows.

Results

The median age at diagnosis of VIN was 42 years (range 25-52 years). The median follow-up was 48 months (range 12-84 months). The median operating time was 10 min (range 5-15 min) depending on multifocal and extent of the lesion. The median healing time was six weeks (range 4-8 weeks) depending on the depth of injury (2nd-3rd surgical plane) and extent of the wound.

All tissue specimens had free surgical margins. In our study population we had ten VIN 1, 35 VIN 2 and ten VIN 3 cases.

Complete response rate at 12-month follow-up was 100%. Partial response rate, at 12 months of follow-up was 0%. Recurrence rate at 12 months of follow-up was 0%.

Complete response rate at 48 months follow-up was 80%. Recurrence rate at 48 months of follow-up was 20%. None of the treated patients progressed to invasive cancer during a mean follow-up of 48 months. These data are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. — Response at 12-month follow-up (n = 55).

	Complete response	Partial response	Recurrence
VIN 1	10 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
VIN 2	35 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
VIN 3	10 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Total	55 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

Table 2. — Response at 48-month follow-up (n = 55).

	Complete response	Recurrence
VIN 1	10 (100%)	0 (0%)
VIN 2	27 (77.14%)	8 (22.86%)
VIN 3	7 (70%)	3 (30%)
Total	44 (80%)	11 (20%)

Discussion

VIN 3 has a certain invasive potential both in untreated (9%) and treated (3.3%) patients. The progression to invasion may occur many years after VIN 3 has been diagnosed [8, 9]. The mean time to progression is 55 months (range 4-216 months) [8]. For that reason patients with VIN 3 should be followed carefully for a very long period of time. Spontaneous regression may occur (1.2%) [8]. In our study none of the treated patients progressed to invasive cancer, during a mean follow-up of 48 months, which might be related to the small number of patients and the close follow-up in our study population.

The choice of therapy for high-grade VIN has been dominated by the premalignant nature of the disease. Although extensive surgery is no longer the advised treatment, standard therapy for patients with VIN still comprises surgical removal of all visible lesions to relieve symptoms and to prevent the development of invasive disease [8]. Currently there is not enough available evidence to support the removal of all involved vulvar skin [8].

In cases of VIN, treatment should be directed towards preservation of the normal anatomy and function of the vulva [10]. Repeat local resections preserve them better than primary extensive surgery [11, 12]. Symptomatic relief is best achieved by local excision instead of a skinning vulvectomy [11, 12].

There are potential advantages of LEEP for treating VIN lesions, particularly those of limited size. These include: low cost of the equipment, avoidance of the operating room, avoidance of the general anesthesia and provision of a specimen [3, 13]. LEEP may be more accurate than laser CO₂ in uncovering foci of early invasion (LEEP uses excision rather than ablation) [3, 13]. In our study all tissue specimens had free surgical margins. The operating time ranged between 5-15 min depending on multifocal and extent of the lesion. From our experience we believe that every gynecologist is capable of performing LEEP on VIN after five to ten supervised applications with a high index of confidence.

The period of tissue repair and degree of postoperative pain were largely related to the overall extent and site of LEEP, rather than the depth of penetration of treated areas. Patients with treated areas ≥ 6 cm² and/or perianal skin included in the treatment field, experienced the longest periods of repair (48 days) and the most severe degree of discomfort [3]. In our study the median healing time was six weeks (range 4-8 weeks) depending on the depth of injury (2nd-3rd surgical plane) and the overall extent of the wound. Keeping in mind the postoperative discomfort, especially over the perianal area (< 1.5 cm from the anus), it is preferable to save islands of normal skin for acceptable healing in extensive lesions. Large VIN lesions can be removed in segments in two appointments (1-2 months apart) [13].

There is no indication that recurrences of VIN 3 depend on the type of surgery used, except cryosurgery, which has a high failure rate [8, 14]. Cure rates are influenced principally by factors other than the specific cytoreductive method [3]. Included among these are later activation of latent HPV DNA, contamination from adjacent HPV positive lesions, skin appendage involvement, positive surgical margins, and immunosuppressed states [15]. However, recurrences do occur significantly more often after involved surgical margins than after free surgical margins [8]. LEEP and laser CO₂ produce similar therapeutic success rates in patients with VIN [3, 14]. In our study all tissue specimens had free surgical margins and the recurrence rate at 48-month follow-up was 20%.

The negative effect of vulvar surgery for the patient is great and irreversible. It has been shown that half of the

women suffer from sexual dysfunction and psychological problems following vulvectomy (radical or simple) [16, 17]. It has also been suggested that postoperative sexual functioning and somatopsychic reactions after treatment for VIN 3 correlated with the magnitude of the excision [16, 17]. In our study none of the patients complained of post-treatment sexual dysfunction.

The main complications in our study population were spot bleeding (10%), instant pain of low intensity (only when the clitoris was operated) and postoperative discomfort (70%) for one to two hours. The newly formed epithelium after a mean period of seven weeks presents excellent topography with little or no disfigurement. In extensive lesions multiple applications of LEEP resulted in a low degree of vitiligo (the thermal effect extended to the 3rd surgical plane).

It is clear that current treatments for VIN are suboptimal and continue to represent a clinical challenge. The best approach is individualized management based on clinical presentation, extent of disease and patient preference.

In conclusion, LEEP may constitute a valuable excisional method for the treatment of VIN. It provides an interpretable specimen of the whole lesion within a few minutes, needs a short period of training, and has low cost.

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